

FTL communication using photon wave function collapse – Thought experiment

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Abstract:

The following thought experiment explores the potential for a "universal now", an absolute frame of reference in the universe. Essentially, a detector can collapse a photon wave function, which another detector can use as statistical proof that the first detector has interacted with the photon wave function, as a form of faster-than-light (FTL) communication.

Keywords: universal now, wave function, faster-than-light (FTL) communication.

1. Introduction

Photons work as wave functions that spread out over space. If something intercepts that wave function, like a detector in the wave functions path, it has a chance to collapse at that point. If the photons wave function collapses at one point, the entire wave function ceases to exist, instantly; according to the Copenhagen Interpretation.

2. Thought experiment

Imagine we have the following:

Photon source (It emits a set, large number of photons every second) - PS

Detector 1 - D1

Detector 2 - D2

D1 is closer to the photon source than D2. But D1 and D2 are also very far from each other. PS is shooting photons directly towards the midpoint of these two detectors, with the wave function spreading out laterally. If D1 begins observing, it is going to collapse photon wave functions, which gives D2 less wave functions to collapse.

In this scenario, both D1 and D2 know that the PS is emitting a set, large number of photons every second. If D2 is constantly observing, it can detect a dip in photon quantity when D1 begins observing, because D1 causes D2 to have less photon wave functions to observe itself.

How might this prove a universal now?

If it works as stated, it proves FTL (Faster Than Light) communication.

D1 can send a signal to D2 by observing the photons, causing D2 to observe less photons in total. D2 interprets this drop in photon count as D1 observing photons. That is information. D2 has gained information about the actions of D1.

This is possible because the wave function collapses instantaneously upon observation. The absence of photons continues travelling in a straight line towards D2, while if D1 wanted to conventionally send a radio message, the path directly from D1 to D2 is longer than the distance the “absence of photons” must travel to D2. Since this absence of photons reaches D2 before the radio signal from D1 reaches D2, D1 has effectively sent an FTL message to D2.

3. Potential experiment

Experimentally, this could be done with the same items. A photon source, and two detectors which can change their own chance of catching a photon, whether through increasing their surface area, or their transparency. This should be able to be done both on earth, and in space.

If the experiment shows information being received at D2 (a drop in photon quantity) before the time a direct signal from D1 would arrive, that is evidence for FTL communication.

If the experiment shows that the information of photon absence is received at the same time as a direct signal from D1 to D2, it means the collapse of the wave function either isn't instantaneous, potentially opening photon duplication methods, breaking conservation of energy, or the universe has a way of not allowing the message to happen.

Image: Visualisation.

Green text: Names of objects.

Black circles: D1, D2, PS.

Black line: Line of aim by PS.

Black parabolic lines: Photon wave function reach.

Blue lines: The shortest path for D1 and D2 to interact with the photon wave function.

Red line: Distance between D1 and D2.

Purple line: Photon wave function collapse and absence due to D1 interaction.